

Deep Learning Models for GNSS-denied Target Navigation

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Abstract. This work tackles the problem of target navigation in Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS)-denied scenarios by adapting two Deep Learning (DL)-based approaches: the Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) and the Neural Hierarchical Interpolation for Time Series (NHITS). These methods are trained on custom created datasets from which the methods learn, after which they are able to make their own predictions. Obtained numerical results via simulations and real testbed reveal that, on the one hand, the proposed methods improve navigation accuracy and are less vulnerable to noise when compared to existing Machine Learning (ML) approaches. On the other hand, the results also exhibit a reduction in training time.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Deep Learning (DL), Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT), Neural Hierarchical Interpolation for Time Series (NHITS), Navigation Indoor.

1 Introduction

Target navigation in Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS)-denied environments is one of the key challenges in future autonomous robots, vehicles and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). Solving this problem allows future developments in the automatization of tasks such as infrastructure inspection [1], surveillance [2], real-time stock monitoring [3], and many more. Generally, these vehicles use GNSS signals to estimate their location and still require certain

amount of human control to navigate themselves, especially in complex environments (tunnels, confined indoor spaces, *etc.*). Moreover, these signals do not penetrate buildings with sufficient quality; thus, alternative means of localization are required.

Considering the fact that there is no uniquely accepted solution to navigate targets in the considered environment, the motivation for this work started with the following research question: *"How can one exploit Deep Learning (DL) tools to semi-autonomously navigate a target in GNSS-denied scenarios?"*. To address the research question, this work is based on the following hypothesis. *"Autonomous target navigation can be achieved through a conjunction of data-driven DL models with statistical estimation methods, where DL models are trained by using predictions of the statistical estimation method to learn and make their own predictions."* More specifically, the current work employs Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) [4] and Neural Hierarchical Interpolation for Time Series (NHITS) [5] models, whose training is accomplished based a on General Trusted Region Sub-Problem (GTRS) estimator, and are then able to make their own predictions, making navigation possible.

The remainder of this work is organized as follows. Firstly, Section 2 states the contributions of the current work to AI-driven Cyber-Physical Systems. Secondly, the Related work is presented, followed by problem formulation in Sections 3 and 4, respectively. Then, the proposed solutions are presented and tested in Sections 5 and 6. Finally, the conclusions and future research directions are described in Section 7.

2 Contribution to AI-driven Cyber-Physical Systems

The system considered in this work fits perfectly in what is considered an AI-driven Cyber-Physical Systems (AI-CPS), *i.e.*, an intelligent system that integrates cyber (computational) and physical (UAV, robot) components, enhanced by AI. The proposed system operates in real-time, processes data from the physical world (acquired radio measurements) to gain awareness about the location of the target, and makes intelligent decisions to optimize performance, enhance autonomy, and ensure reliability. The work demonstrates how AI models can be adapted to target navigation problems, making tasks such as real-time warehouse stock monitoring and counting, infrastructure (pipelines, bridges) inspection, and autonomous transportation of tools, supplies and organs possible. Moreover, the proposed solutions can easily be installed on the edge (for instance in a robot, vehicle or UAV, with the required hardware resources), allowing real-time data processing and decision-making, thus contributing to the embedded AI-CPS field.

3 Related Work

The usage of artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms for target navigation has attracted significant attention in the research community in re-

cent years. In [6], the authors proposed a deep neural network formed by a Convolution Neural Network (CNN) that retrieves local spatial features from measurements, and afterwards a deep Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) module that deals with temporal features. In [7] computer vision and DL are used. More specifically, resorting to images captured via an onboard camera and a CNN it is possible to predict the location and orientation of the target. The usage of CNNs is also proposed in [8], where a deep-CNN is used to analyze objects and compute the trajectory with this information. An LSTM combined with Ultra Wide Band (UWB) data is proposed in [9] to estimate the location and navigate the target. Afterwards, an Extended Kalman Filter is used to combine the prediction with other onboard sensors to compute the final estimations. A similar approach is presented in [10], but this time the LSTM is trained using predictions from existing algorithms. With the training stage, the LSTM is able to learn and make its own location predictions. A similar logic is presented in [11]; however, this time, the authors resort to two LSTMs trained using different algorithms. The final location estimation is performed by averaging the two LSTMs.

In contrast with the described solutions, on the one hand the proposed models do not resort to expensive hardware like cameras and other sensors, achieving low-cost solution and allowing better agility. On the other hand, the more advanced architecture of the TFT and NHITS models enables a better feature extraction from the training data when compared to the LSTM and CNN, resulting in increased accuracy.

4 Problem Formulation

Considering a 2-dimensional (2D) scenario containing a mobile target (for instance, a UAV, robot, vehicle, *etc.*, with sufficient computational power to process small AI models) and N stationary reference points, where their positions are denoted by $\mathbf{x}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and $\mathbf{a}_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$, respectively, for a given time instant t . This work seeks accomplishing navigation of the target throughout a given scenario, by resorting to intermediate points deployed at predefined locations and range measurements acquired from wireless communication with the reference points. The work considers a nearly constant velocity model, where the target changes its direction of movement according to

$$\left[(\mathbf{x}^{(t+1)})^T, (\mathbf{v}^{(t+1)})^T \right]^T = \mathbf{S} \left[(\mathbf{x}^{(t)})^T, (\mathbf{v}^{(t)})^T \right]^T, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{S} is a state transition matrix represented as

$$\mathbf{S} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \Delta & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \Delta \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

with Δ being the sampling interval between two consecutive time steps, and

$$\mathbf{v}^{(t)} = \boldsymbol{\nu}^{(t)} \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\varphi^{(t)}) \\ \sin(\varphi^{(t)}) \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^2 \quad (2)$$

is the velocity vector of the target, $\varphi^{(t)}$ represents the azimuth angle between the current target's location and destination, and $\boldsymbol{\nu}^{(t)}$ is the target's speed, a parameter used to smooth out the arrival at the (intermediate) destination point. This is accomplished by introducing a threshold distance, τ , to control the target's speed with respect to its vicinity to the (intermediate) destination. Thus, on the one hand if $\tau > 4$, $\boldsymbol{\nu}^{(t)}$ is computed via

$$\boldsymbol{\nu}^{(t)} = \boldsymbol{\omega}^{(t)} \cdot P_{vmax} \quad (3)$$

being P_{vmax} is the maximum speed allowed. On the other hand, when $\tau \leq 4$, $\boldsymbol{\nu}^{(t)}$ is computed via

$$\boldsymbol{\nu}^{(t)} = \boldsymbol{\eta}^{(t)} \cdot \left(\frac{\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(t)}}{\tau} \right)^\gamma \quad (4)$$

where, γ is a smoothing factor and $\boldsymbol{\eta}^{(t)} = \mathbf{x}_{\text{dest}} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t)}$, $\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(t)} = \|\boldsymbol{\eta}^{(t)}\|$ is the distance between the current target location estimate and the desired destination.

To estimate the location of the target, terrestrial radio measurements (for instance, by employing UWB, Wireless Fidelity (Wi-Fi), Bluetooth, Zigbee technologies) are exploited by extracting distance (range) measurements from the received signal. This can be accomplished via different techniques such as Time-Of-Flight (TOF) [12, 13] or RSS [14, 15]. Note that the choice between which technique to employ (*e.g.*, TOF or RSS) can have major influence on localization accuracy, but it is ultimately determined by the user's resources. Thus, the k -th distance sample ($1 \leq k \leq K$) between the target at time t and a reference point i is defined as

$$d_{i,k}^{(t)} = \|\mathbf{x}^{(t)} - \mathbf{a}_i\| + \delta_{i,k}^{(t)} + n_{i,k}^{(t)}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \quad k = 1, \dots, K, \quad (5)$$

where the Euclidean norm is denoted as $\|\bullet\|$, the non-line of sight bias introduced by possible obstacles is denoted as $\delta_{i,k}^{(t)} \geq 0$ and $n_{i,k}^{(t)}$ stands for the measurement noise, modeled as a zero-mean Gaussian random variable with standard deviation $\sigma_{i,k}^{(t)}$, *i.e.*, $n_{i,k}^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{i,k}^{(t)})$. With the goal of adding robustness against outliers, and for the sake of simplicity, the median of the K distance samples, $d_i^{(t)}$, is used in the following derivations. In this way, resorting to the maximum likelihood (ML) criteria [16] and from (5), the target's location at time t can be estimated as

$$(\hat{\mathbf{x}}^{(t)}, \hat{\delta}_i^{(t)}) = \arg \min_{\mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \delta_i^{(t)}} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{2(\sigma_i^{(t)})^2} \left(d_i^{(t)} - \|\mathbf{x}^{(t)} - \mathbf{a}_i\| - \delta_i^{(t)} \right)^2. \quad (6)$$

However, since (6) is highly non-convex and under-determined, it is difficult to solve the ML estimator directly.

5 The Proposed Methodologies

This section describes how to adapt TFT and NHITS models for target navigation. A brief description on how the models make their predictions, and how they are trained, is described in the following subsections.

5.1 Proposed Models for Target Navigation

In this work, two existing DL models are customized to predict the location and navigate the target. The first one is the TFT proposed in [4] and the second one is the NHITS proposed in [5]. First, a dataset is created using the predictions of the GTRS algorithm for a fixed $\sigma = 3$ meters. Afterwards, this dataset is split into train and validation and fed to each model (TFT, NHITS and the LSTM in [10] is used as a benchmark) so that they can be trained. After the training, various performance metrics can be extracted (*e.g.*, RMSE, Loss and training time). These steps are visually represented in Fig.1 for better comprehension.

Fig. 1. Visual representation of the system model.

5.2 Training of the models

The TFT and NHITS models require the dataset to be formatted into 4 columns as follows: "*unique_id; ds; y; trend*", where *unique_id* is an identifier, *ds* is an index, *y* is the location estimation (X- or Y-axes) and *trend* is an auxiliary feature used to train the model. In this way, for demonstration purposes, predictions from the GTRS algorithm proposed in [17] were chosen to populate the dataset (namely, the 'y' column).

This algorithm circumvents the ML problem in (6) by transforming it into a GTRS framework as follows. First, weights are introduced with the purpose of assigning more trust to *closer* reference points as

$$w_i^{(t)} = \frac{(d_i^{(t)})^{-1}}{\sum_{i=1}^N (d_i^{(t)})^{-1}} \quad (7)$$

instant t . In addition, no inertial parameters were considered in the motion of the target.

To test the proposed methods, a dataset with size $look_back$ is created at each waypoint and is fed to the model. As an example, considering the initial position of the target $[10, 5]^T$ and the next waypoint $[75, 5]^T$, the following dataset is created for the X- and Y-axes: $testX = [10, 11, 12, 13, 14]$, $testY = [5, 5, 5, 5, 5]$. Note that, the $testY$ dataset is constant since, considering the second waypoint, one desires to move horizontal only. The model then uses these datasets to make its own predictions. Each prediction is added to the dataset, making it dynamic. A visual representation of this behavior can be seen in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Visual representation of how the system makes predictions until it reaches the final destination.

The remaining simulation parameters were defined as follows: $N = 6$, $\sigma = 3$, $\tau = 1$, $look_back = 5$ and the number of times the model iterates throughout the dataset, $Epochs = 300$.

The average trajectory and its deviation for the TFT model can be seen in Fig. 3a. From Fig. 3a, one can see that the TFT model achieved a nearly perfect trajectory even when the training data is noisy.

Next, the NHITS model was tested and the achieved results can be seen in Fig. 3b. This figure reveals that when compared with TFT, the predictions are not as accurate, thus indicating more vulnerability to noise present in the training data. Nonetheless, the overall trajectory still closely resembles the desired one.

To further validate both models, a comparison with the existing LSTM model [10] was also performed. The trajectory predicted by the LSTM can be seen in Fig. 3c. From this figure it is visible that the LSTM exhibits an overall less smooth trajectory, presenting in some cases, high fluctuations, for instance after the target has changed direction.

To assess the learning of the models, the last 10 positions of the dataset were used as test and the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) between the estimation and the test dataset was computed. These results, together with the average training time of all models are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. RMSE and training time comparison for the three models.

Model	RMSE X (m)	RMSE Y (m)	Training time (s)
TFT	0.63	1.22	24.4
NHITS	0.72	3.06	11.2
LSTM	0.72	7.07	186.1

Table 1 reveals that the most accurate model in terms of learning is TFT, followed by NHITS and LSTM. Regarding the training time, the fastest is NHITS, followed by TFT. In both cases they are roughly $7\times$ faster than the LSTM, making them more suitable for dynamic scenarios where the retraining of the models is required.

To conclude this section, real experimental tests were also conducted. These tests were performed using MakerFabs DW3000 ESP32 UWB micro-controllers that implement both the target and the reference points. The micro-controllers were programmed so that the target is able to compute the distance to each anchor by exchanging messages and measuring the time it takes to send and receive them back. In these experimental tests, an office with a width of 4.53 (m) and a length of 3.26 (m) was used, which can be seen in Fig.3 (d)-(f) alongside the obtained results. In this scenario, instead of shelves, steel cabinets visible in Fig. 4, were used as objects and the attenuation was defined by measurement calibration. The movement of the target was created using a fixed size step along the trajectory. In addition, no inertial parameters were included in the motion of the target. The parameters remain the same apart from N , which is now 7. Given the reduced size of the scenario, the size of the acquired dataset was 27 samples. As this is not sufficient to run the models, extrapolation was performed by computing the average between two subsequent positions to obtain a new one. This strategy doubled the size of the data set. From Fig. 3 (d)-(f), one can see that, on the one hand, the TFT and NHITS models minimize the distance towards the desired trajectory, despite some deviations in the latter part. On the other hand, the LSTM closely matches the GTRS predictions, and consequently presents higher fluctuations overall, especially in the initial part of the trajectory. Overall, considering the size of the dataset, and the error introduced by the GTRS used in the training stage, all models achieve relatively good results, being that TFT and NHITS require significantly reduced training time and navigation steps, and still introduce minimal errors in terms of trajectory when compared to the ideal case.

To summarize, and given that the models produce different numbers of estimates, one way to quantify the results was to make normal projections of the

Fig. 3. Navigation performance in simulated/experimental environment: the solid blue line denotes the ideal trajectory, the blue cross represents the initial position and the blue circle represents the final destination.

Fig. 4. The real scenario environment: a) Setup used in the tests, where the reference points are placed on the walls and the tag is placed on a chair connected to a computer; b) The metallic cabinets used as obstacles; c) ESP32 UWB.

estimates onto the line depicted by the desired trajectory and calculate the average distance between the points and the lines as the error, *i.e.*, the average ARMSE was calculated according to

$$ARMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{MC} \sum_{t=1}^T \|\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}\|^2}{T \times MC}}$$

where T is the number of iterations the model took to reach the final destination, $\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)}$ is the point of projection of the estimation, $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}$, onto the desired trajectory in the t -th iteration.

Table 2. *ARMSE* for the trajectory, distance from the destination comparison ($\|x_{dest} - \hat{x}_{final}\|$) and average number of iterations required to complete the scenario.

Model	<i>ARMSE</i> (m)	$\ x_{dest} - \hat{x}_{final}\ $ (m)	Iterations
TFT Simulation	0.55	0.84	148
NHITS Simulation	0.86	1.07	189
LSTM Simulation	0.80	0.37	222
TFT Real Testbed	0.10	0.06	37
NHITS Real Testbed	0.09	0.29	16
LSTM Real Testbed	0.11	0.48	53

Table 2 reveals that, in the simulations, the TFT model achieves the lowest RMSE, but the LSTM reaches closer to the final destination. In contrast

with the simulations, in the real testbed, the NHITS model achieves the lowest RSMSE and the TFT achieves a closer distance to the final destination. In both experiments, the new models require a lower number of iterations to conclude the respective scenarios, which not only reduces their running time, but also preserves energy resources due to lower number of computations. Overall the new models outperform the LSTM both in terms of RMSE, distance to the destination and number of iterations required to complete the scenario.

7 Conclusions and future work

This work proposed adapting two AI methods to solve the problem of target navigation in GNSS-denied environments. By training the models using existing data, they were able to make their own predictions afterwards. The obtained simulation and real testbed results corroborate that the proposed methods reveal less vulnerability to noise and an accurate overall trajectory estimation when compared to the existing LSTM, while reducing training time and the number of iterations to reach the desired destination.

Future research will focus on integrating obstacle avoidance strategies, as well as eliminating the need for the intermediate destination points to enhance and expand upon the current work.

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